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Policy brief: The role of trust in science for effective policy and societal progress

Executive summary

Trust in science is essential for evidence-informed policymaking and societal progress. This policy brief, based on the 2nd VERITY Online Cluster Meeting held on 11 December 2024, brings together insights from key European projects (VERITY, POIESIS, IANUS, and PREPARED) and the European Commission to explore how trust can be strengthened through responsible research, citizen engagement, and improved science-policy collaboration. Discussions highlighted the urgent need to address misinformation, institutional fragmentation, and weak public engagement. The annex includes a list of the speakers, detailing their contributions and the focus of their discussions during the meeting, as well as a summary table that breaks down the challenges, recommendations, and key actors involved. Policy recommendations focus on fostering structured science-policy interactions, enhancing science communication, promoting research integrity (RI), and expanding the science-for-policy (S4P) ecosystem across Europe. Strengthening trust in science is a democratic imperative, requiring coordinated action to ensure that research informs policy decisions and supports solutions to complex global challenges.

1. Introduction

Trust in science plays a central role in democratic governance and effective policymaking. As the complexity of societal challenges increases, so too does the demand for reliable, evidence-informed decision-making.

#Together for Societal Trust in Science, Research And Innovation

Yet, the erosion of public trust—exacerbated by politicised science debates, disinformation, and insufficient engagement—threatens the legitimacy and utility of scientific advice. This policy brief draws on insights from the 2nd VERITY Online Cluster Meeting, where researchers, policymakers, and representatives from the European Commission convened to discuss how trust in science can be supported and operationalised within the science-for-policy (S4P) framework.

2.Context and methodology

The meeting, held online on 11 December 2024, brought together representatives from four Horizon Europe projects (VERITY, POIESIS, IANUS, and PREPARED) and the European Commission. It included expert presentations and interactive discussion focused on trust in science and science-policy collaboration.

The meeting aimed to:

- Share evidence and strategies to enhance trust in science,
- Support the development of a forthcoming position paper, and
- Facilitate exchange and cooperation across projects and institutions.
- Insights were gathered through thematic content analysis of the discussions and synthesised into this brief.

3.Key challenges

The following core issues were identified:

1. Erosion of public trust in science, driven by misinformation and the politicisation of scientific debates. As shared by VERITY and based on the Eurobarometer Media and News Survey 2022, 26% of EU citizens primarily use social media for news, and 29% rely on it for information about science and technology—heightening their exposure to disinformation and undermining trust in expert sources.

- Fragmented science-policy interactions, which limit the effective uptake of scientific evidence in decision-making.
- Weak institutional support for RE, RI, and ethical science communication, leading to inconsistencies in how research is presented and perceived.
- Limited public engagement, reducing the legitimacy and inclusivity of research and innovation.

4. Insights on building trust and strengthening science-policy collaboration

The Cluster Meeting reinforced that trust is not based solely on the robustness of evidence but also on how science is conducted, communicated, and connected to societal values. Key insights include:

- Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles, including transparency, ethics, and public participation, are central to building trust.
- Citizen engagement, such as participatory research and co-creation processes, helps to align research with societal needs and build legitimacy.
- Cross-sector and interdisciplinary collaboration can break silos in science-policy interfaces, allowing for more coherent and responsive decision-making.
- Science communication is increasingly critical. To counter misinformation, communication must be timely, accessible, and ethical. Literacy initiatives and transparent narratives help restore credibility in scientific discourse.
- Institutional change is needed to embed RI and support open science (OS) practices. These frameworks should also protect researchers facing public backlash or harassment.
- Policy responsiveness is vital. The European Commission's S4P initiatives, including Next ERA, encourage more formalised structures for cooperation between science and policy.

- Trust in science is context-specific and continuously shaped through transparent, credible, and participatory processes.

5. Policy recommendations

To support trust in science and ensure research evidence is effectively used in policy, the following recommendations are proposed:

Annex:

Speakers list

The following experts contributed to the discussions:

- **Agata Gurzawska** (VERITY)
Trust-building strategies from the VERITY project.
- **Georgios Papanagnou** (European Commission's Directorate-General Research and Innovation)
Insights on evidence-based policymaking and the next ERA framework.
- **Fara Lledó San Mauro** (European Commission Science for evidence-informed policymaking, S4P)
Bridging the science-policy gap: Current challenges and opportunities.
- **Hub Zwart** (IANUS)
Integrating RI into policymaking.
- **Panagiotis Monachelis** (VERITY)
Data on social media usage and misinformation trends.
- **Leonidas Ananiadis** (POIESIS)
Citizen engagement in science: Best practices from the POIESIS project.
- **Kalle Videnoja** (PREPARED)
PREPARED project perspectives on S4P in times of crises.

Challenge category	Challenge	Recommendations	Key Factors
Communication	Erosion of public trust in science, driven by misinformation and politicisation	Expand media literacy Promote transparent, ethical science communication	Science communicators, media, education ministries, academies
Policy	Fragmented science-policy interaction Limited capacity for knowledge translation	Establish regular dialogues Co-design research agendas Train policymakers in evidence uptake Promote cross-sector knowledge exchange	EC (S4P Unit), advisory bodies, research funding organisations (RFOs), JRC, think tanks, higher education institutions
Production	Weak institutional support for RI and ethical communication	Advance OS practices Establish crisis communication standards Protect researchers from harassment	Research performing organisation (RPOs), research ethics committees (RECs), research integrity offices (RIOs), EU NCPs (European National Contact Points)
Participation	Limited public engagement, weakening inclusivity and legitimacy	Support participatory science Foster RRI practices	Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), museums, public institutions, and RRI initiatives